

27 the conducted experiments. The growth rate of the newly formed particles ranged from 3 – 11 nm
28 h^{-1} with particles reaching a diameter of 20-25 nm after a few hours. The nucleation rate was
29 estimated using an aerosol dynamics model and was found to be in the range of 500 to 25000
30 particles $\text{cm}^{-3} \text{h}^{-1}$ for the different experiments. These results support the hypothesis that ammonia
31 at levels of several ppb can accelerate or even cause new particle formation at least in the
32 environment of the Eastern Mediterranean.

33

34 **1. Introduction**

35 Atmospheric aerosol can be produced from many natural or anthropogenic sources and
36 plays a significant role in Earth's climate and in public health (Haywood and Boucher, 2000; Pope
37 et al., 2002). Aerosols can affect climate either by scattering and absorbing incoming solar
38 radiation (direct effect) or by acting as cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) thus affecting reflectivity
39 and lifetimes of clouds (indirect effect). New particle formations (NPF) through nucleation of low-
40 volatility vapors can be an important source of atmospheric aerosols and is responsible for close
41 to 50% of the global CCN (Merikanto et al., 2009). Newly formed particles either grow to larger
42 sizes through condensation or are scavenged by larger preexisting particles through coagulation.
43 Self-coagulation is another growth process for the newly formed particles. The competition
44 between these processes determines how many of those new particles will grow to become CCN
45 and how fast this will happen. NPF has been observed in many areas around the world including
46 all types of environments (urban, rural, forests, remote, marine, etc.) (Kulmala et al., 2007;
47 Kerminen et al., 2010; Wang et al., 2017; Yao et al., 2018; Zhu et al., 2019; Saha et al., 2019).

48 Previous studies have underlined the importance of sulfuric acid for NPF in most
49 environments (Jaeger-Voirol and Mirabel, 1989; Weber et al., 1996; Laaksonen et al., 2000;
50 Sipila et al., 2010). Additional studies have shown the importance of ammonia and amines as
51 vapors that can accelerate the nucleation rate of sulfuric acid with water by stabilizing the initial
52 clusters of sulfuric acid. (Weber et al., 1998; Kirkby et al., 2011; Jen et al., 2014; Glasoe et al.,
53 2015). Low and extremely low volatility organic vapors play a major role in the growth of the new
54 particles and may be also participating in the nucleation process itself (Yli-Juuti et al., 2011; Zhao

55 et al., 2014; Ehn et al., 2014; Mohr et al., 2019). In marine environments iodine compounds have
56 been identified as vapors that can form new particles (McFiggans et al., 2010; Sipilä et al., 2016;
57 He et al., 2021) Wang et al. (2020) have recently reported fast growth rates of newly formed
58 particles at some atmospheric conditions due to the condensation of ammonium nitrate. The
59 preexisting aerosol (condensation sink), the availability of gaseous precursors and the
60 meteorological conditions all affect the intensity and frequency of NPF events in the atmosphere.

61 Extensive monitoring of NPF events has taken place in many sites in Europe (Manninen et
62 al., 2010; Dinoi et al., 2021) and the eastern Mediterranean (Pikridas et al., 2012; Berland et al.,
63 2017; Kalkavouras et al., 2017; Kalivitis et al., 2019; Hussein et al., 2020; Brilke et al., 2020).
64 Siakavaras et al. (2016) reported frequent nucleation events in Thessaloniki, a major urban center
65 in northern Greece. On the other hand the nucleation frequency in southern Greece is relatively
66 low (compared to central and northern Europe) especially during the summer (Kaliivitis et al.,
67 2008; 2019). Kopanakis et al. (2013) observed nucleation events only in 13 out of the 157 days of
68 measurements in the Akrotiri station, in Crete. Kalkavouras et al. (2020) reported a relatively low
69 20% nucleation frequency during the summer in Finokalia, Crete. Particle size distribution
70 measurements in five stations in Greece (Athens, Patras, Thessaloniki and Finokalia) during the
71 summer of 2012, showed low NPF frequency in Patras and Finokalia (Vratolis et al., 2019).
72 Pikridas et al. (2012) provided evidence that ammonia or amines may be the missing reactants that
73 are responsible for the lack of nucleation in this sunny relatively clean area with available sulfur
74 dioxide.

75 In this work we test the hypothesis that in an environment such as the Eastern
76 Mediterranean during the summer, in which despite the high sunlight intensity, rapid
77 photochemistry, moderate to low particle levels, always available sulfur dioxide and reasonable
78 levels of both biogenic and anthropogenic VOCs, nucleation events are rare due to the relatively
79 low ammonia levels. The experiments took place during summer in Patras, Greece in an
80 environment with low nucleation and growth frequency (Patoulias et al., 2018; Vratolis et al.,
81 2019) using a dual chamber system. The use of this innovative experimental set up, in a location
82 in which nucleation is infrequent, allows us to perturb the atmosphere (at least a few cubic meters
83 of it) in order to identify the reactant that is limiting the new particle formation. The use of two
84 chambers to correct for various complications arising from these challenging measurements is an

85 additional novelty of this work. Both chambers were filled with ambient air, ammonia was added
86 to one of them, and the evolution of the aerosol was followed in both chambers.

87

88 **2. Methods**

89 **2.1 Dual chamber system**

90 A dual chamber system was deployed as part of the 2019 summer PANACEA
91 (PANhellenic infrastructure for Atmospheric Composition and climatE change) campaign in
92 Patras, Greece. Measurements were conducted in the outskirts of Patras (population 200.000
93 people) between July 15 until August 15, 2019, in the Institute of Chemical Engineering Sciences
94 (ICE-HT), approximately 8 km from the city center. The dual chamber system consisted of two
95 identical Teflon chambers (1.3 m³ each) located inside a structure that included the chambers and
96 five panels of UV lights used for illumination purposes ($J_{\text{NO}_2}=0.25 \text{ min}^{-1}$). Ammonia was added in
97 one of the chambers (perturbation chamber) while the other one was used as the reference. The top
98 of the structure can be removed, and natural sunlight was used if the weather conditions allowed
99 it. Details about the design and testing of the dual chamber system can be found in Kaltsonoudis
100 et al. (2019).

101 The major difference between the conditions in the reference chamber and the ambient air
102 is that the chamber has a little lower concentrations due to losses in the sampling system. The UV
103 light is also a different in some experiments in which artificial light was used. Other experiments
104 used natural sunlight, so this was not an issue. Other differences include the interactions of the
105 pollutants inside the reference chamber with the walls of the chamber (for example losses of
106 particles but also some vapors to the walls during the experiment). Finally, the pollutant levels in
107 ambient air in the site may change as the wind brings new air masses to the area, while the air mass
108 inside the reference chamber remains the same as that present in the site at the time of the filling
109 of the chamber.

110

111 **2.2 Experimental procedure**

112 Before the beginning of each experiment both chambers were flushed with ambient air for
113 approximately 2 hours. The main purpose of the flushing is the conditioning of the chambers and
114 the sampling lines to the environmental conditions and composition thus minimizing losses of
115 volatile or semivolatile compounds to the walls of the system. During this preparation period both

116 chambers were swept for 20 min using an ionizer fan (Dr Schneider PC, Model SL-001) to reduce
117 the charges on the chamber walls thus reducing the particle wall losses (Jorga et al., 2020). After
118 the chambers were ready, they were filled with ambient air using a metal-bellows pump (Senior
119 Aerospace, model MB-302). The concentrations of pollutants in both the gas and particulate phases
120 were then characterized for one hour. A 0.25 in copper tube was used for the particle phase
121 measurements and a 0.25 in PTFE tube was used for the gas measurements. The instruments were
122 located inside a room next to the chambers to avoid their exposure to high temperatures. The
123 distance from the chambers to the instruments was approximately 4 m. An automated valve was
124 used to alternate sampling between the two chambers. The valve was synchronized with the
125 sampling periods of the various instruments and sufficient time was allowed between each
126 sampling change to flush any remaining air from the previous measurement.

127 After the characterization phase, ammonia was injected through a heated line into the
128 perturbation chamber using a glass syringe. The concentration of the injected ammonia was
129 estimated using the volume of the chamber and the amount of liquid ammonia injected and it varied
130 from 20 to 200 ppb. These estimates are probably upper limits because losses of ammonia in the
131 inlet system and the walls of the chamber are expected. Even though the ammonia levels used in
132 this study are relatively high, they are still in the range of observed concentrations in the
133 atmosphere. For example, Dammers et al. (2017) measured ammonia concentrations in the
134 Netherlands up to 300 ppb. The fact that we have several measurements at concentrations higher
135 than those used by Kirkby et al. (2011), but still relevant to the atmosphere is a nice feature of this
136 work. After the ammonia injection, the top cover of the system was removed, and the chambers
137 were exposed to natural sunlight. If the wind speed is high, even if only the top cover is off, the
138 chambers may be destroyed by the wind. So, during these conditions the chamber system was kept
139 completely covered and the UV lights were used instead of natural sunlight for the corresponding
140 experiment.

141 At the end of the experiment, ammonium sulfate seeds were injected into both chambers
142 to measure the size dependent particle wall-loss rate constants using the method described in Wang
143 et al. (2018). After the end of the particle wall-losses period both chambers were flushed once
144 again with ambient air for approximately 2 hours, to remove the ammonium sulfate and any
145 remaining pollutants and to prepare them for the next experiment. The potential interactions of our
146 experimental system with the chamber walls are the reason for the use of the second (reference)

147 chamber. Any interactions will also be present there and will be observable and therefore we can
148 correct for them. Desorption of ammonia from the walls was tested with blank experiments the
149 following day from a perturbation experiment. The system was filled with ambient air, with no
150 addition of ammonia and the system response was tested. In all the blank experiments we did not
151 observe any nucleation in the perturbed chamber due to the ammonia that had been added in past
152 experiments.

153

154 **2.3 Instrumentation**

155 The chemical composition of the aerosol was monitored using a High-Resolution Time-of-
156 Flight Aerosol Mass Spectrometer (HR-ToF-AMS) from Aerodyne Research Inc. Two Scanning
157 Mobility Particle Sizers (SMPS) were used to measure the number size distributions from 9-160
158 nm (classifier model 3080, CPC model 3775) and from 14-730 nm (classifier model 3080, CPC
159 model 3025A) respectively. The sample flow was dried before reaching the AMS and SMPS
160 systems using a Nafion dryer. A suite of gas monitors was used to measure the concentrations of
161 NO_x (Teledyne 201E/501), SO₂ (Thermo Scientific Model 43i), and O₃ (Teledyne 400E).

162

163 **2.4 Aerosol dynamics model**

164 A zero-dimensional aerosol dynamic model was used for the simulation of nucleation,
165 condensation and coagulation inside the perturbation chamber (Capaldo et al., 1999). The
166 multicomponent aerosol size distribution is described using 270 size sections covering the
167 diameter range from 1 nm to 1 μm. The aerosol components include sulfate, ammonium, organics,
168 and others with the latter assumed to be non-volatile and inert during the few hours of the
169 simulation period.

170 The condensation rate of H₂SO₄ to a particle of diameter D_p is described using the modified
171 form of the Fuchs-Sutugin equation (Hegg et al., 1991; Kreidenweis et al., 1991) given by:

172

$$173 \quad J = 2\pi D D_p F(Kn) A (P - P_o) \quad (1)$$

174 where D is the diffusivity of the vapor air (set to 0.1 cm² s⁻¹ in this application), Kn is the Knudsen
175 number (that is the ratio of the air mean free path to the particle radius), $F(Kn)$ is a coefficient
176 correcting for free molecular effects given by:

$$177 \quad F(Kn) = \frac{1+Kn}{1+1.71Kn+1.33Kn^2} \quad (2)$$

178 and A is a coefficient correcting for the interfacial mass transport limitations described by the
 179 accommodation α_e ,

$$180 \quad A = \left[1 + 1.33Kn F(Kn) \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_e} - 1 \right) \right]^{-1} \quad (3)$$

181 Finally, P is the bulk H_2SO_4 vapor partial pressure and P_o is its partial pressure at the particle
 182 surface. An accommodation coefficient of 0.02 for the condensation of H_2SO_4 on the aerosol
 183 particles is assumed (Van Dingenen and Raes, 1991). The vapor pressure of H_2SO_4 at the aerosol
 184 surface can be estimated from the data of Bolsaitis and Elliott (1990). Values less than 10^{-3} ppt
 185 were found for the conditions of our experiments and therefore the surface vapor pressure of H_2SO_4
 186 in our mass transfer calculations was assumed to be zero.

187 Brownian coagulation between all particles is simulated solving the discrete coagulation
 188 equation (Seinfeld and Pandis, 2016):

$$189 \quad \frac{dN_k(t)}{dt} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} K_{j,k-j} N_j N_{k-j} - N_k \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} K_{k,j} N_j \quad k \geq 2 \quad (4)$$

190 The generalized coagulation coefficient $K_{1,2}$ for the collision of two particles is calculated as:

$$191 \quad K_{1,2} = 2\pi(D_1 + D_2)(D_{p1} + D_{p2})\beta \quad (5)$$

192 where D_1, D_2 are the individual Brownian diffusion coefficient for the particles, D_{p1}, D_{p2} are the
 193 particle diameters and β is the Fuchs correction factor (Fuchs, 1964). Because of the high
 194 resolution of the size distribution, coagulation can be simulated accurately by directly calculating
 195 the coagulation rates between each of the size sections and moving the particles to the
 196 corresponding size bin.

197

198 **2.5 Data analysis**

199 The condensation sink (CS) is a metric of the ability of the pre-existing aerosol population
 200 to remove vapors from the system by condensation. The CS values were calculated using the
 201 aerosol distribution between 14-700 nm, as measured by the SMPS and the properties of sulfuric
 202 acid as the condensing vapor. The CS is given by:

$$203 \quad CS = 2\pi D \sum_i \beta_{mi} D_{pi} N_i \quad (6)$$

204 where D is the diffusion coefficient of sulfuric acid, β_m is the transition-regime correction factor,
 205 D_p the diameter of the particle and N the respective number concentration in each size bin of the
 206 SMPS.

207 Using the initial SO₂ concentration in the perturbed chamber and the condensation sink we
208 can estimate the sulfuric acid concentration according to:

$$209 \quad [H_2SO_4] = k_{OH} \frac{[SO_2][OH]}{CS} \quad (7)$$

210 where k_{OH} is the reaction constant of SO₂ and OH which is equal to $8.5 \times 10^{-13} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ molecule}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
211 at 298 K (Demore et al., 1997), [SO₂] and [OH] are the concentrations of sulphur dioxide and
212 hydroxyl radicals respectively, and CS is the condensational sink as calculated from Equation 7.
213 For the hydroxyl radical concentration, we assumed an average value of $5 \times 10^6 \text{ molecules cm}^{-3}$.
214 Equation (7) is based on the assumptions that the only sulfuric acid source is the oxidation of SO₂
215 from OH radicals, its major sink is its condensation onto the aerosol surface, and the system is at
216 pseudo-steady state.

217

218 **3. Results and discussion**

219 **3.1 Initial conditions**

220 Thirteen perturbation experiments were conducted during the study (Table 1). Two of them
221 took place during the night using UV lights and the rest during midday. Natural sunlight was used
222 in two experiments while UV lights were used during the rest.

223 The main components of non-refractory PM₁ in the beginning of our experiments were
224 organics (46.6±6.5%) followed by sulfate (37.1±4.5%), ammonium (14.3±1.8%), nitrate
225 (1.5±0.5%) and chloride (0.5±0.4%). The average oxygen to carbon ratio (O:C) (Canagaratna et
226 al., 2015) in the chambers after filling them with ambient air was 0.68±0.1, indicating an already
227 oxidized OA. In order to check if any contamination was occurring during the flushing and filling
228 processes we calculated the theta angle (Kostenidou et al., 2009) between the organic mass spectra
229 of the ambient air and the OA in the two chambers. The theta angles were less than 6° in all
230 experiments, indicating negligible contamination during the filling process.

231 The initial concentration of the SO₂, NH₃, O₃ and NO_x inside the chambers after the filling
232 process were approximately within 10% of their ambient values. The initial concentrations of these
233 gases in the two chambers differed by less than 3%. More than 70% of the ambient PM₁ was
234 transferred in the chambers in most experiments. The initial PM₁ levels were quite low ranging
235 from 0.6 to 4.2 μg m⁻³. The atmosphere of Patras was quite clear during these experiments. The
236 initial conditions in all experiments are summarized in Table 1.

237 **3.2 New particle formation and growth**

238 The conducted experiments were classified in three different classes based on the
239 observations of new particle formation in the two chambers. In class A experiments, nucleation
240 and particle growth occurred in only the perturbed chamber, in class B nucleation and particle
241 growth happened in both chambers and in class C when there was no detection of new particle
242 formation in either chamber.

243

244 **3.2.1 Nucleation and growth only in the perturbed chamber**

245 Nucleation and growth of the new particles to sizes above 9 nm only in the perturbed and
246 not in the reference chamber were observed in 6 out of the 13 performed experiments. Figure 1
247 depicts the particle number concentration N_9 ($D_p > 9$ nm) after corrections for particle losses to the
248 chamber walls and the sampling lines, inside the two chambers for a typical Class A experiment.
249 During Exp. A1 the initial concentration of SO_2 was 0.7 ppb and of O_3 equal to 58 ppb. After the
250 injection of ammonia (approximately 150 ppb) the UV lights were turned on ($t=0$ h) illuminating
251 both chambers. The N_9 particle number concentration start increasing in the perturbed chamber
252 approximately 1.5 h after the lights were turned on, reaching close to 4000 cm^{-3} , almost double its
253 initial concentration value. The observed delay of the N_9 particle number concentration in the
254 perturbed chamber is attributed to the time needed for the particles to grow to larger sizes so that
255 they could be detected by our available instrumentation. The N_9 concentration in the control
256 chamber remained within 5% of the initial levels. Figure 2 shows the measured number
257 distributions in the two chambers after correction for particle losses. The formation and growth of
258 the new particles in the perturbed chamber is evident. With a CS of 0.0026 s^{-1} the H_2SO_4
259 concentration was calculated to be of the order of $3 \times 10^7 \text{ molecules cm}^{-3}$. Assuming that nucleation
260 started at $t=0$ the measured initial growth rate in the perturbed chamber was on average 4 nm h^{-1} .
261 This rate is based on the time of growth of the nucleation mode to 15 nm. For this experiment 3.8
262 h were required for the growth of the new particles to 15 nm so the estimated growth rate is
263 approximately 4 nm h^{-1} . The newly formed particles at the end of the experiment (after 5 h from
264 the illumination) grew to approximately 20 nm. The experiment was stopped at that point because
265 a significant fraction of the air in the two chambers had been sampled.

266 The estimated initial growth rates (refers to the average rate for the period between the start
267 of the experiment and the time the particles reach a diameter of 9 nm) for the daytime experiments

268 A1, A2, A4, A5, and A6 varied from 3.5 to 8 nm h⁻¹ and were correlated with the estimated H₂SO₄
269 levels (R²=0.76) (Table 2). Experiments A1, A5 and A6 had similar CS and H₂SO₄ levels and
270 resulted in similar initial growth rates (Table 2). The slope of the growth rate versus sulphuric acid
271 linear regression for the daytime experiments was 1.4 (nm h⁻¹ molecule⁻¹ s) and the intercept was
272 low and equal to 0.05 nm h⁻¹.

273 Experiment A3 was conducted during the night (the chambers were filled with ambient air
274 at 21:00 so it has relatively different behaviour than the rest. If this experiment is included in the
275 growth rate versus H₂SO₄ correlation, the R² drops to 0.27. This probably suggests that the
276 estimated OH levels are not accurate in this case and therefore the H₂SO₄ is probably also a lot
277 more uncertain than in the other experiments. Also, the growth process may be different with
278 organic vapors playing a more significant role.

279

280 **3.2.2 Nucleation and growth in both chambers**

281 In 4 (B1 to B4) out of the 13 perturbation experiments, new particle formation and growth
282 was observed in both chambers (Table 2). This suggests that the ambient air had already the
283 potential to form new particles without the addition of ammonia.

284 Figure 1b shows the *N*₉ concentration in the two chambers during Exp. B1. The initial
285 levels of SO₂ in both chambers were 0.8 ppb and approximately 150 ppb of ammonia were added
286 to the perturbation chamber. Half hour after the exposure of the chambers to UV light the *N*₉ in
287 both chambers started increasing with higher concentrations in the perturbed chamber. The number
288 concentration of the particles in the perturbed chamber reached close to 6000 cm⁻³ almost three
289 times the initial levels. The concentration in the baseline chamber increased by approximately 50%
290 to 3000 cm⁻³. The newly formed particles in the perturbed chamber at the end of the experiment
291 reached a mode diameter of 26 nm (Fig. 3) with an initial GR of 5.5 nm h⁻¹. The growth rate of the
292 particles in the reference chamber was only 10% lower than in the perturbed one (Fig. 4)
293 suggesting that the addition of ammonia probably significantly influenced the nucleation rate but
294 had a small effect on the growth rate.

295 We tested the hypothesis that the appearance of the new particles in the reference chamber
296 was due to a sampling error, caused by some cross contamination of the two samples as the same
297 sampling line was used. We compared the shape of aerosol size distributions in the two chambers.

298 The nucleation mode distribution in the reference chamber was wider (Figure S1), a strong
299 indication that these were different particle populations sampled by our system.

300 The condensation sink in the class B experiments was on average 0.0024 s^{-1} quite similar
301 to the 0.0023 s^{-1} in the A experiments so the pre-existing particle mass was quite similar in the two
302 classes of experiments. Also, the average SO_2 was practically the same (0.83 ppb for the B
303 experiments and 0.82 ppb for the A experiments). The average ammonium concentration for the
304 class A experiments was only 20% higher than that of Class B-experiments. The ammonium levels
305 in this area are determined to a large extent by the sulfate levels. Adding the similarity of the UV
306 intensity, it is clear that the major factors (sunlight, condensational sink, SO_2 availability) usually
307 determining nucleation rates were not the reason for the weak nucleation and growth in the
308 reference chamber in these experiments. The presence of sufficient ammonia levels is one of the
309 possible explanations for this behaviour.

310 The observed growth rates in these B-class experiments varied from 3.5 to 11.3 nm h^{-1} and
311 were a little higher on average than those in the A group of experiments. Adding these four
312 experiments to the linear regression of the growth rate versus sulphuric acid reduced the R^2 to 0.43,
313 but the slope remained the same, while the intercept increased to 0.7 nm h^{-1} . These provide some
314 weak evidence of the involvement of more compounds, probably organics, in the growth of these
315 newly formed particles in this second group of experiments.

316

317 **3.2.2 Nucleation and growth not observed**

318 In three of the experiments C1-C3, we did not observe growth of new particles to the size
319 of 9 nm. It is still possible that there was nucleation, but the growth may have been too slow (less
320 than 2 nm h^{-1}). We were able to measure only particles larger than 9 nm. If the growth rate in those
321 experiments was less than 2 nm h^{-1} then the particles would not be reaching the 9 nm threshold
322 during the experiment. Figure 1c depicts the N_9 number concentration during Exp. C1. The initial
323 concentration of SO_2 was 1.3 ppb in this experiment. The number concentration after correction
324 for particle losses remained constant at close to 2200 cm^{-3} and the corresponding number
325 distributions changed little during the experiment (Fig. 4). Exp. C1 had the lowest initial levels of
326 ozone of all the experiments (Table 1), around 12 ppb, a factor of four lower than the average
327 concentration. The low O_3 levels were probably due to the highest NO_x levels (27 ppb) in this air
328 mass.

329 Exp. C2 was conducted in the early evening (the chamber was filled with ambient air
330 around 19:00 LT) and the lowest detectable particle size for this experiment was 14 nm because
331 of technical difficulties. Finally, Exp. C3 had relatively low levels of sulfuric acid (2.5×10^7
332 molecules cm^{-3}) compared to the rest of the experiments, a low estimated level of injected ammonia
333 (20 ppb) and natural sunlight.

334

335 **3.3 Particle composition**

336 The mass concentration of the major components of PM_{10} (sulfate, organics, nitrate,
337 ammonium) in the two chambers, after correcting for chamber particle wall losses, remained
338 practically constant during all experiments. The corrected for wall losses mass concentration inside
339 both chambers during Exp. B1 are shown in Figure 5. Considering the uncertainty of the wall loss
340 correction, the maximum increase of the concentration of the corresponding secondary PM
341 components during the few hours of the experiments should have been a few percent or less. This
342 will be an important constraint for the analysis of these experimental results with the aerosol
343 dynamics model in the next section.

344

345 **3.4 Estimation of nucleation rate using an aerosol dynamics model**

346 We used our aerosol dynamics model to simulate the growth and coagulation of the
347 particles in the perturbed chamber assuming a nucleation rate. Our goal is to use the observations
348 to constrain the nucleation rate that could not be measured directly. The model uses as inputs the
349 temperature and relative humidity during the experiments and is initialized with the measured
350 particle number distribution at time zero. There are three adjustable parameters in the model: the
351 duration of nucleation, the nucleation rate, and the condensation rate. Nucleation is assumed to
352 start at time zero and a constant nucleation rate is assumed for the duration of the event. This is a
353 necessary assumption given the available measurements. This constant rate is in practice an
354 average rate for the estimated duration of the event. The condensing components are assumed to
355 have practically zero vapor pressure. The three parameters were chosen so that the model
356 predictions were in good agreement with the observations of particle number concentration and
357 size distribution and also the mass concentration. The change in the condensation sink during the
358 experiments was modest (reduction 10-30%) however other important parameters like the

359 concentration of the species participating in the nucleation process were probably changing at the
360 same time.

361 Figure 6 shows the measured and the predicted particle number, surface and volume
362 concentrations in the perturbed chamber for Exp. A1. A nucleation event with rate equal to
363 $J_1=9500 \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ and duration of 3 h together with a condensation rate of 3.2 ppt h^{-1} was needed
364 to reproduce the observations. For much lower condensation rates the particles did not grow to
365 detectable sizes and for higher condensation rates the predicted PM mass increase was not
366 consistent with the small observed mass concentration change. We performed sensitivity analysis
367 around these central values and values of $J_1=9500\pm600 \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ remained consistent with the
368 observations. The average errors during the simulation were 6% for the number concentration,
369 16% for the surface concentration and 17% for the mass concentration. Other effective nucleation
370 rates (e.g., J_3 or J_9) can be estimated with our approach, but this would require reconfiguration of
371 the model so that the size distribution would start at the corresponding diameter threshold.

372 The predicted and observed evolution of the aerosol number distributions are shown in
373 Figure S2. The differences for the smaller particle sizes are partially due to the losses of these
374 particles in the sampling and measurement systems.

375 Table 3 summarizes the estimated nucleation rates together with the corresponding
376 durations of the nucleation events and the required condensation rates for all experiments in groups
377 A and B in which nucleation and growth were observed. The estimated J_1 rates varied from 500 to
378 $25000 \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$. These values are between those in ambient measurements and those of the CLOUD
379 laboratory experiments (Fig. S3).

380 These results can be roughly compared to the CLOUD measurements for sulfuric acid-
381 ammonia nucleation (Kirkby et al., 2011) in the 2×10^7 - 10^8 molecules cm^{-3} H_2SO_4 concentration
382 range that was estimated for our experiments. The CLOUD measurements for the highest ammonia
383 levels used suggested a $J_{1.7}$ rate of approximately $500 \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ for H_2SO_4 concentration equal to
384 5×10^7 molecules cm^{-3} . For experiment A4 we estimated the same H_2SO_4 concentration and a
385 nucleation rate of $400\pm 200 \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ (Fig. S3). While this agreement is probably fortuitous, overall,
386 our estimated nucleation rates are in general consistent (considering their uncertainties) with the
387 CLOUD measurements for the ammonia-sulfuric acid system assuming that the rate does not
388 increase further as ammonia increases above 1 ppb.

389

390 4. Conclusions

391 A dual chamber system was used to investigate the hypothesis that ammonia is often the
392 limiting reactant for new particle formation in the Eastern Mediterranean, using a new
393 experimental approach in one of the areas with the lowest new particle formation frequency in
394 Europe during the summer. Ambient air characterized by relatively aged air masses in southern
395 Greece was used as the starting point of our experiments. Ammonia was added in one chamber
396 while the second was used as a reference. Using two chambers adds to the novelty of this work,
397 allowing for corrections due to the interactions between the chamber walls and the reacting gases
398 and particles. To the best of our knowledge this is the first study that uses such an experimental
399 set up for determining the role of a reactant, like ammonia, in new particle formation under realistic
400 environmental conditions.

401 In 6 out of the 13 experiments (46%) the addition of ammonia led to the formation and
402 then growth to detectable size (approximately 10 nm) of new particles, while no formation of
403 particles was observed in the reference chamber. In another 4 experiments (31%) the addition of
404 ammonia significantly enhanced the formation of new particles, but new particles were formed
405 also in the reference chamber. Finally, in the remaining 3 experiments (23%) we could not observe
406 new particle formation. New particles may have been formed and may have not grown to
407 detectable sizes in these experiments. The formed particles grew to sizes around 20-25 nm after 5
408 hours, with an estimated initial growth rate ranging from 3 to 11 nm h⁻¹. These results suggest that
409 the presence of ammonia, at least at the high levels used in our study, allowed almost half of the
410 time the formation and growth of particles that would not be formed otherwise. In one quarter of
411 the cases ammonia significantly increased the nucleation rate compared to the ambient conditions.
412 Finally, in the last quarter of the cases the high ammonia levels did not cause nucleation and growth
413 to detectable sizes.

414 We should note that we did not observe ammonium nitrate formation in any of our
415 experiments despite the high ammonia levels. This is probably due to the combination of relatively
416 low nitric acid levels and high temperatures during our study. This suggests that ammonium nitrate
417 was not formed in the perturbed chamber after the ammonia injection and did not contribute to the
418 particle growth in our experiments.

419 An aerosol dynamics model was used to estimate the J_1 nucleation rate constrained by the
420 measured aerosol number distribution and mass concentrations. The used box model does not

421 directly include the ammonia concentration or a nucleation parameterization but is used instead to
422 provide estimates of the nucleation and growth rates that are consistent with the measurements.
423 New particle formation occurred even at the lowest ammonia levels (20 ppb) used in these
424 experiments. The nucleation rate in the perturbed chamber ranged from $500 \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ up to 25000
425 $\text{cm}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$. Coupled with the estimated sulfuric acid concentrations these rates are in general
426 consistent (within one order of magnitude) with both ambient measurements and those of the
427 CLOUD lab experiments for the nucleation rates in the sulfuric acid-ammonia-water system.
428 Nucleation was observed even at the lower ammonia levels used in this work (20 ppb), and the
429 estimated nucleation rate was quite high. This result is applicable to environments with high
430 ammonia levels like the Netherlands or the Po Valley. The ammonia levels in these areas are often
431 similar to those in our experiments.

432 The two major new advances of this work are first the use of a new experimental technique
433 that allowed us to test the hypothesis of Pikridas et al. (2012) which was based on circumstantial
434 evidence (the ratio of ammonium to sulfate in the particles and the wind trajectories) and second
435 the results of the experiments that strongly support the hypothesis. A technique to estimate the
436 nucleation and growth rates from these data even without measurements of sub-10 nm particles is
437 an additional contribution.

438 Experiments in which new particles formation was observed in both chambers show one
439 of the advantages of using a dual chamber system in such experiments. The use of the reference
440 chamber can help verify if the conducted perturbation was responsible for the observed change.
441 Future experiments with this system should include measurements of the sub-10 nm part of the
442 aerosol size distribution and accurate measurements of the NH_3 concentration.

443

444 **Data and code availability.** The laboratory results and the aerosol dynamics code are available
445 from the authors (spyros@chemeng.upatras.gr).

446

447 **Supplement.**

448

449 **Author contributions.** SDJ performed the experiments, analyzed the results, and wrote the paper.
450 KF helped in the performance of the experiments. DP wrote the aerosol dynamics code. SNP was

451 responsible for the design of the study and the synthesis of the results and contributed to the writing
452 of the paper.

453

454 **Competing interests.** The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

455

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464

465 **5. References**

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714 **Table 1:** Initial conditions in the conducted experiments.

Exp.	Category	PM ₁	O ₃	NH ₃ ^c	SO ₂	NO _x	RH
		(μg m ³)	(ppb)	(ppb)	(ppb)	(ppb)	(%)
Exp. A1	Class A	1.6	58	150	0.7	3.6	40
Exp. A2 ^a		4.2	47	25	1.6	12.1	50
Exp. A3 ^b		0.9	49	200	0.6	5.6	42
Exp. A4		0.6	52	120	0.5	4.4	45
Exp. A5		3.6	54	120	0.6	3.7	40
Exp. A6		3.7	52	150	1	7.2	40
Exp. B1	Class B	2.2	45	150	0.8	6.7	50
Exp. B2		1.6	49	25	1.1	8.4	56
Exp. B3		1	41	200	0.6	8.3	58
Exp. B4		2.2	56	120	0.8	4	40
Exp. C1	Class C	3	12	150	1.3	27	48
Exp. C2 ^b		2.5	56	75	0.6	7.5	38
Exp. C3 ^a		2.2	50	20	0.6	11	52

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716 ^a Experiments illuminated by natural sunlight

717 ^b Experiment conducted at night

718 ^c Estimated concentration in the perturbation chamber.

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725 **Table 2:** Nucleation time, nucleation rate and condensation rate in the experiments were NPF was
 726 observed in the perturbed chamber.

Experiment	Initial GR (nm h ⁻¹)	Condensation sink × 10 ³ (s ⁻¹)	H₂SO₄ × 10⁻⁷ (molecule cm ⁻³)
Exp. A1	4	2.6	3
Exp. A2 ^a	8	3.5	5
Exp. A3 ^b	5.5	0.8	8
Exp. A4	6.5	1.1	5
Exp. A5	3.5	3.1	2
Exp. A6	3.7	2.9	4
Exp. B1	5.5	3.1	3
Exp. B2	11.3	2.1	6
Exp. B3	7	2.4	3
Exp. B4	3.5	2	4
Exp. C1	0	2.8	5
Exp. C2 ^b	0	2.1	3
Exp. C3 ^a	0	2.5	2

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728 ^a Experiments illuminated by natural sunlight

729 ^b Experiment conducted at night

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733 **Table 3:** Nucleation time, nucleation rate and condensation rate in the experiments that NPF was
 734 observed in the perturbed chamber.

Experiment	Nucleation time (h)	Nucleation rate (cm⁻³ h⁻¹)	Condensation rate (ppt h⁻¹)
Exp. A1	3	9500 ± 600	3.2 ± 0.3
Exp. A2 ^a	2	10000 ± 1000	4.5 ± 0.4
Exp. A3 ^b	2	500 ± 100	3.8 ± 0.4
Exp. A4	2	600 ± 200	4.5 ± 0.3
Exp. A5	2	6500 ± 1000	2 ± 0.2
Exp. A6	3	7000 ± 500	3 ± 0.4
Exp. B1	2.5	15000 ± 1500	4.5 ± 0.5
Exp. B2	1.9	25000 ± 2000	10 ± 1
Exp. B3	2	5000 ± 700	4.5 ± 0.5
Exp. B4	2.5	14000 ± 1000	3 ± 0.2

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736 ^a Experiments illuminated by natural sunlight

737 ^b Experiment conducted at night

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771 **Figure 1:** Wall loss corrected number concentration N_9 in the three different types of experiments,
772 a) NPF and growth only in the perturbed chamber (Exp. A1), b) NPF and growth in both chambers
773 (Exp. B1) and c) no NPF observed (Exp. C1). The dashed line marks the time that ammonia was
774 injected in the perturbed chamber. At $t=0$ both chambers were illuminated with UV light.

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776 **Figure 2:** Wall loss corrected measured number distributions in the two chambers for Exp. A1.

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794 **Figure 3:** Wall loss corrected measured number distributions in the two chambers for Exp. B1.

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809 **Figure 4:** Wall loss corrected measured number distributions in the two chambers for Exp. C1.

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828 **Figure 5:** The wall loss corrected mass concentration of a) organics, b) sulfate, c) ammonium and
 829 d) nitrate in the control (blue dots) and perturbed (red dots) chamber during Exp. B1. The purple
 830 shades region represents the time that the chambers were under UV illumination.

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844 **Figure 6:** Measured and simulated number, surface, and volume concentration in the perturbed
 845 chamber after turning UV lights on for Exp. A1. The error bars in the measured values are
 846 calculated from the uncertainty in the particle wall loss correction and represent two standard
 847 deviations.
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